

ANALYSIS OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY IMPROVEMENT OF ELECTRICAL SYSTEMS OF TEXTILE ENTERPRISES

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Abstract: *The general goal of designing and optimizing electrical systems of textile enterprises is to achieve the minimum production cost corresponding to the required operational performance. It shows that the use of variable speed controls in an enterprise can reduce energy consumption by up to 50%. In the process of modeling electric motors using MATLAB simulink software of existing processes in textile enterprises, motor torque control and overall power demand were analyzed and recommendations were developed based on this.*

Key words: *Textile plant, electric drive systems, functional analysis, high-efficiency asynchronous motors, operating costs, energy saving, MATLAB simulink, energy demand volume.*

It is often said that the concept of reliability in a broad sense means that electrical equipment produced by a manufacturing enterprise is more "reliable" than another enterprise. In such cases, the "reliability" of electrical equipment is taken into account when relative costs are not important. Reliability in a broad sense is the ability of a subject to perform one or more functions required for specified conditions [1].

The result of reliability is determined by comparing products obtained on the basis of updated or previous technologies, their energy consumption differences and, in turn, the differences in lost energy.

The main indicators of the main percentages are:

- technical characteristics;
- appearance (saving the specified system, comfortable working conditions) [2];
- unique raw material (condition after drying of silk);
- thread production technologies;
- technical competence in production;
- test to estimate the average working life of motors;

- environmental conditions.

Application of functional analysis methods can evaluate the future performance of the system. For example, the asynchronous motor control system used in textile enterprises consists of eight subsystems (AC / DC converters, rectifiers, filters, inverters, asynchronous motor, control unit, power supply, interface and communication of the operating system with the operator). (Figure 1)

Such management systems can be used in the existing procedures in textile enterprises and in the objects of product control of production enterprises.

Based on current research, we can see the following:

- the most frequent accidents occur due to high temperature;
 - 25% of accidents can be prevented with the help of management;
- the failure rate of modern electrical systems is from 6% to 9% per year;
- the increase in utilization rate is closely related to reliability [3];
- uncertainty in the analysis of the real demand for electricity;
- Occurrence of overload due to changes in the operating system;
- Over the course of the system's operation, they tend to wear out and therefore require an increase in technological maintenance parameters;
 - Formation of short-term overload at high ambient temperatures of 40 °C.
- Use of small motors where there is a large difference between the motor power and the standard nominal power;

After establishing an analysis of control systems in the application of electric vehicles, several problems were selected based on this work description during preparation and experiments.

It is the most important to choose the main techniques for controlling DC machines used in enterprises.

1. Figure 1. An asynchronous motor control system used in electrical drives at a textile enterprise.

The need for easy integration and reliable operation of the actuator (power command) in the process of automatic integration corresponds to variable frequency dynamic indicators [4]. Today, the number of hydraulic, pneumatic and automatic systems is increasing, which provides speed and high precision control and power/load ratio, durability and ease of maintenance.

The motor torque is controlled by the displacement of the stator current and the corresponding torque generating part. The rotor current is kept constant by the flux component of the stator current. The total stator current is externally controlled to maintain the rotor current at the desired torque under steady-state conditions, and changes the stator voltage to maintain the rotor current constant under transient conditions (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The model of adjusting the torque of the alternating current motor (AC) at the textile enterprise in the Matlab program

The torque control of the machine is carried out by controlling the stator current and torque, which selects one of the six non-zero and two non-zero commutator vectors shown in Figure 2. Errors are defined by ΔT_e and ΔP_{ss} respectively [5].

$$\Delta T_e = T_{ref} - T_e$$

$$\Delta \psi_s^S = \bar{\psi}_{sref}^S - \bar{\psi}_s^S$$

In torque control, the electromagnetic torque given by the equation causes a change in the developed torque as the angle g between the two vectors changes as the angle between the sinusoidal functions is shown in Figure 3:

$$T = \frac{3}{2} P \bar{i}_s \cdot j \bar{\psi}_s$$

Figure 3. The angle γ between the two vectors has changed
The electromagnetic moment is calculated using the following equation:

$$T_e = \frac{3}{2} \cdot P \cdot (\psi_{ds}^s i_{qs}^s - \psi_{qs}^s i_{ds}^s)$$

In the Matlab program, it will be possible to run the model created by entering the parameters of the electric motor in the textile enterprise.

%% Tizim parametrlari

imax = 150; % Maksimal tok [A]

Rs = 3; % Faza bo'yicha stator qarshiligi [Ohm]

p = 4; % qutblar soni

Vdc = 400; % o'zgarmas kuchlanishi [V]

load ee_srm_data; % yuk SRM oqimining xarakteristikasi

%% Nazorat parametrlari

Ts = 5e-6; % Namunaviy vaqt [s]

Tsc = 10*Ts; % Namuna vaqtini boshqaring [s]

Kp = 0.001; % Hozirgi tekshirgichning mutanosib ravishda ortishi

Ki = 0.05; % Joriy tekshiruvchi integratorining o'zgarishlari

Kaw = 1000; % Hozirgi tekshirgich tashqi qarshi o'zgarishlar

Based on the above parameters, we can get the following characteristics between 1.5 seconds.

4.1 Fig. The graph of the change in the current amplitude. (A) Fig. 4.2. Graph of change of current I. (A)

4.3 Fig. Electric motor speed graph [rad/sec]

4.4 Fig. Graph of torque change (N M) Fig. 4.4. Graph of change of rotor angle.

Based on approximate torque and speed control, the above calculations differ by only 2.4%. Thus, a small difference in percentages means the correctness of the developed model.

Asynchronous electric motors used in textile enterprises based on intelligent electrical control systems are designed to be controlled based on the above model. Based on this, we will be able to evaluate them in the following order.

An optimal management process is applied to the above model and includes the following:

- minimization of net consumption;
- minimization of operational costs;
- to maximize efficiency;

- maximum security;
- quality according to the given standard.

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